

Invitation Email Template

Subject: Invitation to Participate in Research on Blockchain Developer Experience

Dear *Participant Name*,

My name is *Research Name, University Name*. I am conducting an academic study on the developer experience in blockchain platforms and would like to invite you to participate.

About the Study:

We are developing the BcDEX Framework, an instrument designed to evaluate developer experience in Blockchain-as-a-Service (BaaS) platforms. Your expertise as a blockchain developer would be highly valuable for validating this framework.

Participation Includes:

1. An initial questionnaire (5–10 minutes)
2. A 60–90 minute interview via videoconference
3. Providing feedback on the framework and practical scenarios

Benefits:

- Contribute to academic research in blockchain software engineering
- Early access to study results
- Reflection on your development practices

If you are interested, please:

1. Reply confirming your availability
2. Complete the initial questionnaire: [link](#)
3. Review and sign the consent form attached

All information will remain confidential, and data will be anonymized in all publications.

Sincerely,

Researcher Name

Researcher Email

Institution / Laboratory Name